

Journal of Economics and Business

Irianti, Andi Adini Thahira, Ashri, Muhammad, and Sakharina, Iin Karita. (2019), Role of Notary Public in Increasing the Ease of Doing Business Index through the Apostille Convention. In: *Journal of Economics and Business*, Vol.2, No.1, 1-9.

ISSN 2615-3726

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.02.01.61

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Economics and Business* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Journal of Economics and Business* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Economics and Business, which includes, but not limited to, Business Economics (Micro and Macro), Finance, Management, Marketing, Business Law, Entrepreneurship, Behavioral and Health Economics, Government Taxation and Regulations, Financial Markets, International Economics, Investment, and Economic Development. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Economics and Business* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Economics and Business.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Role of Notary Public in Increasing the Ease of Doing Business Index through the Apostille Convention

Andi Adini Thahira Irianti¹, Muhammad Ashri², Iin Karita Sakharina³

¹Notary Magister Program, Faculty of Law, Universitas Hasanuddin

^{2,3}Faculty of Law, Universitas Hasanuddin

Corresponding Author: Andi Adini Thahira Irianti, Notary Magister Program, Faculty of Law, Universitas Hasanuddin. Email: adinithahira@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aims to analyze the role of the notary in international business practices and analyze the position of the Apostille Convention in increasing the Ease of Doing Business Index in Indonesia. This is a normative research, utilizing interviews and document studies as the technique of gathering data. The data utilized are primary law sources that are used in this research, which are information attained by the author from direct interviews with authorized officials, as well as secondary law sources that provide explanations in correlation to the primary law sources. The data is analyzed using qualitative analysis, with a descriptive based conclusion made. In the discussions, the author concludes that the role of a notary in the international business practices can be divided into (1) registration of limited liability companies through an online system, and (2) establishment of a foreign investment limited liability company and export-import. The author continues by providing essential explanations on the position of the Apostille Convention in increasing EoDB, by elaborating (1) The Apostille Convention and the obligations and public document legalization procedures, (2) Ease of Doing Business Index, (3) Impact of the Apostille Convention in increasing EoDB, and (4) Application of the Online Single Submission (OSS) system. It is concluded that the Apostille Convention does not guarantee the increase of EoDB, even though the role of a notary is regarded as highly essential in the international business practices, which include the process of issuing authentic deeds, provide counseling on the law processes in establishing companies and legalization of related documents to investments. The role of the Apostille Convention is not significant as the convention only arranges matters related to public documents and not indicators of the EoDB.

Keywords: Notary, Ease of Doing Business, International Business, Apostille Convention, Public Document

1. Introduction

Interactions between subjects that occur in this world have developed and are increasingly unlimited. These activities impact on many aspects, one of which is the legal aspect. The impacts that correlate to the aspects of law causes the crossing of the legal system to widen. In civil law, for example, the relationship between citizens and other citizens in the practice of international trade has made the boundaries of the separation between legal systems visibly unclear, as business relationships are built up frequently based on specific legal systems and across jurisdictional boundaries (Czinkota, 2003).

Globalization in the field of trade and business as well as the birth of free markets has also led to patterns of cross-border relations that require an understanding by practitioners involved in it, including legal practitioners. This understanding is meant by expanding their intellectual horizons and skills regarding the prevailing international legal system and rules. For example, the legal profession of corporate lawyers will need to understand the legal system of a business partner's country over the legal system of the company's business partners in addition to the national legal system in which the company is located. Even the need for a legal system is stronger if there is a dispute with other business stakeholders whose legal systems are different (Elnizar, 2008).

Legal professionals who must also prepare themselves for international business transactions are the notary profession. The history of the work of the notary has been known since humans knew the act of writing. Therefore, the work of a notary is very closely related to writing as the work of a notary is to record particular documents that are considered important in legal relations between parties.

These critical documents which later became the products of the notary profession were used in the activities of international business transactions both in the form of authentic deeds and underhanded deeds. Unfortunately, this notary product only applies locally, which if it is to be used in international relations, a legal process is needed because of differences in the jurisdiction.

This legalization is carried out to guarantee the correct notary signature even if it does not cover the contents of the document. A document can be declared credible if it meets two qualities, namely reliability, and authenticity. A public document can be declared to have met the reliability requirements if the information in it is accurate information per what happened. Whereas, the document is declared to have met the authenticity requirements if the contents of the document are following what was intended by the author and are not in a damaged condition. Legalization of documents is the process of identifying a document to determine that the document is legal, issued, and signed by the authorities (Zablud, 2006).

This is indicated by the need to prove the document to various interested parties. The document must be considered correct insofar as it is not proven otherwise by other parties. By carrying out the process of legalizing this public document, prosecutions from other parties can be prevented regarding the validity of a document.

The process of legalization of public documents originating from abroad involves a complicated, lengthy procedure that requires not a small amount of money (Gautama, 2002). If it is associated with investment activities, of course, this natural process of legalization has a negative impact. The convoluted process and the amount of costs needed in the document legalization process affect the magnitude of the flow of foreign investment activities in a country.

The complexity of the process of legalizing public documents does not mean that the solution to be chosen is to abolish the legalization process. Because, if the legalization process is eliminated, it will affect the certainty of public documents originating from abroad (Chancellor Publication, 1996). On October 5, 1961, a convention was produced in the Hague, the Netherlands, aimed at removing the requirements for diplomatic or consular legalization rather than foreign documents that were public documents. The Convention in question is the Convention Abolishing the Requirement of Legalization for Foreign Public Documents (hereinafter referred to as the Apostille Convention).

The scope of this convention is to apply to what is called public documents and documents that have been made in the territory of one of the participating countries and will be carried out in the territory of one of the other participating countries.

The business climate will directly affect the quality of people's lives. The government is currently working hard to realize a better business climate in Indonesia to prosper the nation's life. Ease of Doing Business (hereinafter referred to as EoDB) is an index compiled by the World Bank as an indicator of how "friendly" a country can cooperate in receiving foreign investment in developing its economy. The World Bank report for the 2016 EoDB entitled "Measuring Regulatory and Efficiency" included Indonesia as the top country in the "Top Reformer" list

because it successfully made significant improvements to 7 of the 10 indicators surveyed. While the EoDB index in 2017 entitled "Equal Opportunity for All" shows that Indonesia managed to rise 15 places from position 106 to 91 and entered the category of 10 countries with the highest ranking jump (Elnizar, 2018).

EoDB surveys and other similar surveys are one of the government tools to measure their performance. By contributing to providing objective and factual input and information, the community and practitioners mean that it has helped the government in carrying out its performance in carrying out the mandate of the welfare of the nation (EoDB, 2008). In the 7th plenary meeting of the Asian Affairs Commission of the International Union of Notaries (CAAs-UINL) and the International Seminar of the Notary Association of Indonesia in September 2017 in Bali, the notary profession has shown a form of full support to the Indonesian Government in improving the EoDB index by covering the theme "Meeting Business Needs (Ease of Doing Business): Opportunities, Challenges, and Roles of Notaries and Other Legal Professions in their Implementation" which also invited a number of stakeholders at the world level.

Improving the guarantee of legal certainty will bring benefits to Indonesia if it is associated with the EoDB index and foreign investment. Not only fresh funds but also technology transfers, educational advancements, soft skills, non-tax revenues and taxes which ultimately expanded Indonesia's economic capacity. When viewed in its entirety, the overall EoDB indicator is very much dealing with applicable legal provisions and enforcement. In other words, everything will be related to legal certainty.

2. Research Methodology

The research method used is a normative legal research method in which data processing is based on the results of research (interviews) and then combined with the data from the study of documents so that we can attain accurate data. The data used are primary data and secondary data. After all the data collection processes, both primary data and secondary data that has been considered valid will then be processed and analyzed using qualitative methods. To obtain a visual reality of the issue, the qualitative data will then be presented descriptively.

3. Role of Notary in Internasional Businesses

The notary in carrying out his duties is based on Law Number 2 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 30 of 2004 concerning Notary Position. In the statutory provisions, it states that the primary task of a notary is to give an absolute agreement to the parties who make it. Thus, the importance of the position of a notary is given by law to make an absolute proof of device or instrument, and therefore the authentic deed is in its essence considered correct. So that is an essential task, especially those who need it in personal or business matters.

Notary plays a vital role in creating legal certainty because of its authentic nature and can be used as a reliable and full evidentiary tool if there are problems related to the deed. Today the need for authentic deeds as proof is increasing along with the increase in business relations in various business fields both from the local to the international scale.

3.1. The Role of the Notary in the Registration of Limited Liability Companies through the Online System

In accordance with the mandate of Article 15 Paragraph (1) of Law Number 2 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 30 of 2004, Notary is authorized to make authentic deeds regarding all acts, agreements, and provisions required by laws and / or it is desired by those concerned to be stated in the authentic deed, guaranteeing the date of making the deed, storing the deed, copy and quotation of deed, all as long as the making of the deeds is not also assigned or exempted to other officials or persons determined by law invited. One manifestation of the provisions required by legislation is that a notary is authorized to make an authentic deed, namely a deed of the establishment made in the form of a notary deed.

Aside from making a certificate of incorporation, a notary also has a role in registering and ratifying Limited Liability Companies. New regulations issued regarding the registration and ratification of Limited Liability

Companies in the form of Minister of Law and Human Rights (PERMENCUMHAM) Regulation Number 4 of 2014 concerning Procedures for Submitting Requests for Ratification of Legal Entities and Approval of Articles of Association and Submission of Notices of Amendments to Articles of Association and Amendments to Data of Limited Liability Companies updated with PERMENCUMHAM Number 1 of 2016, concerning Amendments to Minister of Law and Human Rights Regulation Number 4 of 2014, concerning Procedures for Submitting Requests for Ratification of Legal Entities and Approval of Articles of Association and Submission of Notification of Amendments to Articles of Association and Amendments to Data of Limited Liability Companies conducted through electronic media (Online). Changes from manual systems to electronic systems or online are expected so that registration or approval can run more efficiently and more effectively (Permatasari, 2017).

Registration and ratification of Limited Liability Companies online are through the Legal Entity Administration System (SABH) which is an electronic information technology service of the Company organized by the Directorate General of General Legal Administration.

Thus, in addition to making a limited company deed of establishment, the notary also plays a role in registering online limited liability companies by entering limited company data, checking all data that has been entered to avoid data entry errors, then signing if the decision to approve the establishment of a limited liability company.

The act of checking data carefully and thoroughly is part of the role, from a series of notary roles in online registration of limited liability companies. Data errors when the process of entering data into the system is something that is not desired by anyone, but sometimes still happens. This situation is indeed not separated from the role of the notary. If a data entry error occurs, the role of the notary is to correct the data before it is inputted or uploaded, and the notary checks the wrong part and matches the data carried by the applicant because if a notary makes a mistake the notary must be responsible for making a new deed at a notary fee, but if the applicant blunders, the notary will convey what should have been made a new deed at the client's own expense.

The existence of an online system in establishing limited companies is a form of convenience for those who want to conduct business activities. However, if an error occurs in inputting data or uploading data from the notary, the notary must be responsible for making a new deed at the expense of the notary, but if the applicant is wrong, the notary will submit the deed at the client's own expense. The notary deed remains valid, but accompanied by a deed of the amendment made by a notary with the same number remains accompanied by new data sent back to Kemenkumham with an online system, which will be followed by the issuance of a new decree.

3.2. The role of a Notary in the Establishment of a Foreign Investment and Import-Export Limited Liability Company

The role of the notary in changing Limited Liability Companies (PT) to Foreign Investment Limited Liability Companies (PMA) is closely related to his authority as stipulated in Law Number 2 of 2014 concerning changes to Law Number 30 of 2004 concerning Notary Position. If the client comes to the notary to ask the notary to carry out his authority concerning the client's request regarding the change in his PT to PMA, then the notary's role is to be able to do several things and the steps below:

1. Providing legal counseling: Providing legal counseling is intended so that the client or the parties know and subsequently understand the procedure regarding the change in PT to PMA.
2. Making authentic deeds: Making authentic certificates is the central role of the notary in carrying out their duties, including in changing PT to PMA.

Thus, the change in PT to PMA is followed by changes in the articles of association and/or changes to the PT data. Therefore, after the BKPM issues approval for the Registration submitted to him, the agreement will then be forwarded to the notary in the framework of amending the articles of association and/or data of the PT as well as making a share sale deed (if the investment is made through share trading).

The procedure for submitting a request for amendment to the Articles of Association and/or PT data by a notary to the Minister of Law & Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia is regulated in the Republic of Indonesia Minister of Law and Human Rights Regulation Number 1 of 2016, concerning Amendments to Regulation of the Minister of Law and Human Rights Number 4, 2014 of concerning Procedures for Submitting Requests for Ratification of Legal Entities and Approval of Articles of Association and Submission of Notification of Amendments to Articles of Association and Amendments to Data of Limited Liability Companies.

Thus, the role of the notary if there is a client or party who comes to the notary who wants to change the PT to PMA, the notary has the duty to accommodate all the wishes of the parties including making agreements desired by each party who wishes to cooperate and provide legal advice or counseling to the parties regarding the steps that must be taken by the parties in the amendment to PMA, which are followed by carrying out their authorities and obligations in accordance with the provisions in the Notary Position Law, Limited Liability Company Law, Foreign Investment Law and other related regulations.

4. The position of The Apostille Convention in Increasing the Ease of Business Index (EoDB) in Indonesia

a. The Apostille Convention

In short, as stated in its preamble, The Apostille Convention aims to remove diplomatic and consular legality requirements or obligations from public documents originating from abroad and replace them with more straightforward procedures. Thus, traffic relations are more smooth. The purpose of the ratification and enactment of The Apostille Convention is as a legal basis for the implementation of simplification of procedures for legalizing public documents. In addition, it is expected that the enactment of The Apostille Convention can facilitate cooperation between participating countries from The Apostille Convention.

For a state actor, ratifying The Apostille Convention will provide tangible benefits. A more effective and efficient document legalization process can facilitate the processing of legal documents used for international business transactions. Nonetheless, some countries have decided not to ratify The Apostille Convention because there are some disadvantages for state actors. Some of the disadvantages include for Indonesia, (1) The excessive activity of Indonesia in international organizations is feared to impose the state budget, and (2) political will to implement the provisions of The Apostille Convention is not classified as the current government priority.

The provisions contained in The Apostille Convention will apply to all public documents that have been made within the territory of one participating country from The Apostille Convention, and those documents will be carried out within the territory of one of the other participating countries of The Apostille Convention. In Article 2 of the Apostille Convention, it is explained that public documents originating from abroad as detailed in the paragraph above do not require legalization and formality to be used in the jurisdiction of one participating country. The only thing that needs to be done to make public documents originating from abroad can be used by giving apostille or allonge.

An apostille is a paper slip attached to the relevant document or can also be attached to the relevant public document. Allonge is a separate paper slip separate from the relevant public documents. Thus, allonge becomes like an attachment to the relevant public documents. Either Apostille or Allonge will include, among other things, the date and registration number of the relevant public document. In the Apostille or Allonge, officials from countries (participating countries in the Apostille Convention) that issue the relevant documents provide a certificate in the form of a certificate that replaces all the requirements for legalization.

Apostille or Allonge is registered with the state agency that issued the document. By having registered the document with the agency in the country that issued the document, the judge from another country (which is also the participating country of The Apostille Convention) can be accepted as a legal document. Apostille or Allonge only validates the authenticity of the signature, capacity or authority of the signatory. In the event that the public document is not accompanied by a signature from the competent authority, apostille or allonge authorizes the identity of the stamp or stamp on the relevant public document.

Apostille or allonge does not ratify the substance or contents of the public document. Based on Article 5 of this Apostille Convention, this apostille or allonge will provide the intensity of the validity of public documents originating from abroad. Furthermore, in Article 6 the Apostille Convention mandates participating countries to appoint a competent authority or institution to issue the apostille or allonge. Article 7 of the Apostille Convention stipulates that the appointing authority or institution must make a register (card index) to record every apostille or allonge that has been issued by the relevant authority or institution.

b. Obligations and Procedures for Legalization of Public Documents

Legalization of documents is the process of identifying a document to determine that the document is legally valid, issued and signed by the authorities. This is aimed at the need to prove the document to various interested parties. The document must be considered correct insofar as it is not proven otherwise by other parties. By carrying out the process of legalizing this public document, prosecutions from other parties can be prevented regarding the validity of a document.

The complexity of the process of legalizing public documents does not mean the solution to be chosen is to abolish the legalization process. Because, if the process of legalizing public documents is eliminated, there will be doubts about the public documents originating from abroad whether the public documents have indeed been issued or signed by the authorities. So, the legalization procedure for public documents originating from abroad is not abolished. The procedure for the legalization of complicated and costly public documents needs to be replaced by a more straightforward procedure, namely by using ratification in the form of issuing a certificate attached to public documents originating from abroad.

Thus, public documents originating from abroad and which have been approved, can be immediately applied in the destination country. The middle ground for ratification of a public document with these simpler terms and procedures is accommodated by the provisions of The Apostille Convention.

c. Ease of Doing Business Index (EoDB)

There are ten indicators used by the World Bank to advance the ease of doing business, which includes (EODB, 2018):

1. First Indicator - *Starting Business*
2. Second Indicator - *dealing with construction permit*
3. Third Indicator - *Registering Property*
4. Fourth Indicator - *Paying Taxes*
5. Fifth Indicator - *Getting credit*
6. Sixth Indicator - *Enforcing Contracts*
7. Seventh Indicator - *Getting Electricity*
8. Eighth Indicator - *Trading Across Borders*
9. Ninth Indicator - *Resolving Insolvency*
10. Tenth Indicator - *Protecting Minority Investors*

d. Impact of The Apostille Convention in increasing the Ease of Business Index (EoDB) in Indonesia

Documents to be used abroad at this time must be legalized by a notary or authorized agency, the Ministry of Law and Human Rights, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and Foreign Country Representatives (the country where the document will be used). However, there are many assumptions that the procedure for legalizing public documents is very complicated and costs a lot. Therefore, there is an assumption that the procedure for legalizing public documents needs to be replaced by a more straightforward procedure. One form of simplification is by using authorization in the form of issuing a certificate attached to public documents originating from abroad. Thus, public documents originating from abroad and which have been approved can be immediately applied in the

destination country. Provisions in the Apostille Convention are considered as a middle ground for the ratification of a public document with more straightforward means and procedures.

In Indonesia, the Apostille Convention has not yet been ratified. Then, does ratifying the Apostille Convention have an impact on increasing the ease of business index (EoDB) in Indonesia? A simple answer to this question is that the Apostille Convention does not guarantee that the ease of business index (EoDB) increases. The Apostille Convention is not significant in increasing the Ease of Business Index (EoDB) in Indonesia. Because of the impact of the Apostille does not assess the truth of the contents of the document but only looks at the authenticity of the signatures in a document or the truth of the stamp from a public institution abroad. Although Indonesia decides in the near future to ratify the Apostille Convention, the ratification would not affect the role of the notary in international business practices. This is because the data from the research results (see figure) shows that the legal documents used for international business transactions are not significant. Thus, if the Apostille Convention is ratified, the role of the notary will not be affected.

e. Implementation of the Online Single Submission (OSS)

Electronic Integrated Business Licensing Services (PBTSE), which is more easily called the generic name OSS is present in the context of business licensing services that are valid in all Ministries, Institutions, and Local Governments throughout Indonesia, which have been carried out through One-Stop Integrated Licensing (PTSP) Besides through PTSP, the community can access the OSS System online at any place and at any time.

The OSS system was built in the context of accelerating and increasing investment and business, by applying licensing to try to be integrated electronically. In the latest regulation on OSS, namely Government Regulation Number 24 of 2018, the Government regulates among other things the types, applicants, and issuance of business licenses; implementation of business licensing; business licensing reform per sector, OSS system, OSS institution, OSS funding; incentives or disincentives for implementing licensing through OSS; solving business problems and obstacles; and sanctions.

OSS whose implementation is regulated in Government Regulation Number 24 of 2018 is a government effort to simplify business licensing and create a model of integrated licensing services that are fast and inexpensive and provide certainty. With the OSS system, business permits will be obtained by businesses in less than one hour. The OSS system began since October 2017 as the implementation of the Presidential Regulation (Perpres) No. 91 of 2017 concerning the Acceleration of Business Execution, and has conducted concept trials in three locations, namely: Purwakarta, Batam and Palu. The design of this Information Technology based system is basically by interconnecting and integrating existing licensing service systems at the BKPM / PTSP Center (SPIPISE), regional PTSPs that use the Ministry of Communication and Informatics's system. Also included are systems from various Ministries and licensing issuing Institutions, including the Indonesian National Single Window (INSW) system, the General Legal Administration System of the Ministry of Law and Human Rights, and the Ministry of Home Affairs Population Administration Information System.

OSS operations are held in the Coordinating Ministry for Economic Affairs supported by INSW and other relevant ministries. But this is only a transitional period while preparing for its permanent implementation at BKPM. PP No. 24 of 2018 is a positive and comprehensive milestone for synchronizing licensing regulations at the Central and Regional Governments. For investments or business activities that are already running, then they can adjust their business licensing through the OSS System, either to obtain a Business Registration Number (NIB) or to extend or change business licenses and or commercial permits. At present, the Coordinating Ministry for Economic Affairs has made the OSS Lounge which is expected to become a standard in all PTSPs. In the OSS Lounge, there are independent services, assisted services, priority services, general investment consultations, and business clinics. Task Force to oversee the process of resolving business licensing has also been established in all Provinces. While the formation of the Task Force at the District / City level has almost finished, only waiting for its ratification in some regencies/cities.

The guidelines for licensing services strive for electronic integrity (OSS), including (OSS, 2018):

1. Making and Activating an OSS Account
2. Obtaining a Business Registration Number (NIB)
3. Location Permit
4. Environmental Permit
5. Building Construction Permit
6. Business License
7. Operational / Commercial Permit
8. Payment
9. Development of Business License and Renewal of Company Data
10. Running Business Activities.

5. Conclusion

The role of the Notary in international business practice is to make authentic deeds related to the establishment of a business entity and to obtain its ratification, conduct legal counseling related to procedures in the establishment of a business entity, and legalize documents related to investment activities.

The position of the Apostille Convention in increasing the Ease of Doing Business in Indonesia is not significant. Because the Apostille Convention only regulates matters relating to the legalization of public documents that are used both inside and outside the country where these are not the leading indicators in the EoDB survey.

References

- Adha Dia Agustin, 2014. "The Independence of Notary in the Civil Partnership of Notary." Retchsidee, Volume 1, Nomor 2.
- Article 1, *the Hague Convention Abolishing the Requirement of Legalization for Foreign Public Documents*. Den Haag: 1961.
- Chancellor Publication. *The International Legalization Handbook*. England: 1996.
- Dewi Padusi Daeng Muri, Galang Prayogo, dan Faisal Arif. 2018. "The Rights and Obligations of Notaries According to Indonesian Law Concerning Notary Position." International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology, Volume 9, Nomor 8.
- Doing Business di Indonesia, <http://eodb.ekon.go.id/pentingnya-survei-ini/>
- Erina Permatasari, dan Lathifah Hanim. *Peran dan Tanggung Jawab Notaris Terhadap Pelaksanaan Pendaftaran Badan Hukum Perseroan Terbatas Melalui Sistem Online*. Jurnal Akta, Volume 4, Nomor 3, September 2017.
- Firdaus. 2014. "Kedudukan Hukum Internasional dalam Sistem Perundang-Undangan Nasional Indonesia". Fiat Justisia Jurnal Ilmu Hukum Volume 8 Nomor 1.
- Gelar Seminar Internasional, INI Dukung Program Kemudahan Berusaha. <http://www.hukumonline.com/berita/baca/lt59b1e2bf2c5ba/gelar-seminar-internasional--ini-dukung-program-kemudahan-berusaha>
- Houston Putnam Lowry. 2011. "Enforcing International Judgements." Jurnal GPSolo, Volume 28, No.3.
- Kementerian Koordinator Bidang Perekonomian Republik Indonesia, *Doing Business in Indonesia*, <http://eodb.ekon.go.id/indikator-eodb/>
- Michael R. Czinkota, dkk. *International Business*. Mason: Hoboken. NJ Wiley. 2003
- Mohamad Tareq Hossain, Zubair Hassan, Sumaiya Shafiq, dan Abdul Basit. 2018. "Ease of Doing Business and Its Impact on Inward FDI." Indonesian Journal of Management and Business Economics, Volume 1, Nomor 1.
- Muhammad Rustamaji. 2013. "Menakar Pengawasan Pemberian Bantuan Hukum Dalam Pandangan Richard A. Posner." Rechts Vinding Jurnal Volume 2 Nomor 1.
- Norman Edwin Elnizar, "Yuk, Pahami Konsep Notaris dalam Civil Law dan Common Law", <http://www.hukumonline.com/berita/baca/lt59d9f5002c20c/yuk--pahami-konsep-notaris-dalam-civil-law-dan-common-law>.
- Pelayanan Perizinan Berusaha Terintegrasi Secara Elektronik, OSS Republik Indonesia, www.oss.go.id

- Peter Zablud. 2006. "*the Operation of the Apostille Convention, Now and into the Future.*" Position Paper for the Australian and New Zealand College of Notaries.
- Priskila Penasthika. 2015. "*Urgensi Akses Terhadap Apostille Convention Bagi Negara-negara Anggota ASEAN dalam Menyongsong Masyarakat Ekonomi ASEAN 2015, Perspektif Hukum Perdata Internasional.*" Jurnal Penelitian Hukum Supremasi Hukum, Volume 24.
- Shidarta. 2006. *Penalaran Hukum Dalam Konteks Ke-Indonesiaan.* CV Utomo: Jakarta.
- Sjaifurrachman. 2007. *Aspek Pertanggungjawaban Notaris dalam Pembuatan Akta.* Mandar Maju: Bandung.
- Soerjono Soekanto. 2009. *Pokok-pokok Sosiologi Hukum.* Rajawali Pers: Jakarta.
- Sudargo Gautama. 2002. *Indonesia dan Konvensi-konvensi Hukum Perdata Internasional.* PT. Almuni: Bandung.
- Suhrawardi K. Lubis. 194. *Etika Profesi Hukum.* Sinar Grafika: Jakarta.
- Sofik Handoyo. 2017. "*An Explanatory Study on the Relationship of Public Governance and Ease of Doing Business.*" Asia-Pacific Management and Business Application, Volume 6, Nomor 2.
- Tan Thong Kie. 2007. *Studi Notariat dan Serba Serbi Praktek Notaris.* PT. Ichtisar Baru Van Hoeve: Jakarta.
- Tristan Canara. 2018. "*The Effect of Ease of Doing Business on Firm Creation.*" Annals of Economics and Finance, Volume 19, Nomor 2.
- Yunani Abiyoso. 2018. "Improving the Ease of Doing Business in Indonesia: Problems Related to Contract Enforcement in the Court." IOP Conference Series Earth and Environmental Sciences.
- Zulfa Djoko Basuki. "*Kemungkinan Indonesia Mengaksesi the Hague Convention Abolishing the Requirement of Legalization for Foreign Public Documents.*" Badan Pembinaan Hukum Nasional.